

FACTORS OF SKIPPING BREAKFAST AND ITS IMPACT TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE-11 GAS STUDENTS IN MSU-SULU SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate the factors contributing to breakfast skipping among senior high school students and assess its impact on their academic performance. The study aimed to identify the reasons behind breakfast skipping and understand how it affects students' overall academic achievement. The researchers employed a quantitative research approach, involving a sample of 105 senior high school students. The sample was divided into seven sections, with 15 participants in each section. Data was collected through structured questionnaires that assessed breakfast consumption patterns, reasons for skipping breakfast, and academic performance indicators. The questionnaires were given to the participants during their regular school hours. A checklist survey or questionnaire was used to gather data on the factors and impact associated with skipping breakfast and the students' GPA. Additionally, correlation analysis was used as a statistical tool to analyze the data. The study revealed several factors contributing to breakfast skipping on the academic performance of the students, and it's not a rare occurrence. And the several impacts of skipping breakfast on academic performance do not make an impact on them. Students who regularly skipped breakfast still gain a good academic performance, meaning they still perform very well. The findings emphasized the importance of breakfast in providing essential nutrients and energy for optimal cognitive function. Having acknowledged the above results, the researchers wish to recommend that further studies be made to find educational institutions that should raise awareness among students, parents, and teachers about the importance of breakfast and its impact on academic performance. This can be achieved through educational campaigns and workshops that promote healthy breakfast habits. Researchers also suggest schools should provide breakfast options for students, ensuring they have access to nutritious meals before starting their classes. And also,

further research is needed to explore specific interventions and strategies that can effectively address breakfast skipping among senior high school students and improve their academic performance.

Keywords: *factors, impact, academic performance, skipping breakfast, quantitative, MSU-Sulu senior high school.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important contribution to an individual's access and one of the best processes of a child's life because it allows us to explore, discover, and do things freely, not repeat what previous generations have done. A stress-free life is important and leads to a healthy mind. Healthy means that learners will not fear to explore life, as they have seen someone who is not afraid but is fair in facing the challenges of the present and the future. In the 21st century, there is always race and tuff competition everywhere in the field of education, and students' academics feel pressure and tension in the academic world to survive in so-called competitions because academic achievement is important for future decisions in life. Breakfast is often called 'the most important meal of the day', and for good reason. As the name suggests, breakfast breaks the overnight fasting period. It replenishes your supply of glucose to boost your energy levels and alertness, while also providing other essential nutrients required for good health. Skipping breakfast among Filipino students has several negative effects on the on the rates of overweight and obesity among students. According to SCISPACE, breakfast skipping negatively affects cognitive skills, including memory, concentration, and academic performance. It is also associated with higher levels of fatigue, depression, and lower self-esteem.

Skipping breakfast can have a huge impact on students' academic performance. Hence, having stomach intact or eating while studying serves as a way of learning for others and learning is an important aspect in education as uttered by Sabbaha et. al., (2024) cited by Abdulmajid et. al., (2024), Balla et. al., (2024) Jarak et. al., (2024), Sabbaha et. al., (2024), Basir et. al., (2024), Usman et. al., (2024), and Sakili et. al., (2024). Breakfast is perceived as healthy and even more important than other meals. Students who skipped breakfast during the week had significantly lower academic performance from 32 to 38 points than those who ate breakfast. Research found that with the increase in breakfast consumption, academic performance also increased. Lack of breakfast is associated with a low nutritional condition and therefore leads to low academic performance (Akeredolu and Okafur, 2015).

Breakfast is common among adolescents, but little research has been conducted on the effects of breakfast on school performance. Furthermore, attention problems partly mediated the relationship between breakfast delay and school performance. This large-scale study emphasizes the importance of breakfast as a determining factor for school performance. Some of the reasons for missing breakfast, and the most common reason for missing breakfast, are "no hunger in the morning, sometimes no time to eat." Some

students have experienced headaches, weakness, and difficulty concentrating when they don't get breakfast. Failure to prepare breakfast can be a problem for students' academic performance, as they can't focus and are constantly distracted in class. However, if we can address skipping breakfast well, it can help improve the performance of students.

Further research is needed to investigate specific mechanisms that affect academic performance by avoiding breakfast. Understanding the reasons why breakfast is avoided and its direct impact on cognitive functions and academic results can help to fill this gap in research. Research gap for the topic. This research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the situation at this specific location and could contribute valuable insights for the university and the wider academic community.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the factors of skipping breakfast among the Grade-11 GAS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High school?
2. What is the level of academic performance of the grade 11 GAS students'?
3. What is the impact of skipping breakfast to the Grade-11 GAS students' academic performance?
4. Is there a significant relationship of factors of skipping breakfast to the academic performance of GAS grade 11?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu SHS, located at Capitol Site, 7400, Jolo, Sulu. ChEd holds a secondary public school at Mindanao State University-Jolo during the school year 2023-2024. This school comprises a senior high school and offers two tracks, which are academic and technical vocational tracks. Under the Academic Track are the General Academic Strand (GAS) and the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Stand (STEM).

Sampling Method

The participants of the study are the general academic strand of Grade 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School located at Capitol Site, 7400, Jolo, Sulu. The number of participants was 105, with 15 students in each GAS section. The participants will then answer the questionnaires given by the researchers to determine the factors and impact of skipping breakfast.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024), Basir et. al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024), Abdulhari et. al. (2024), Hadjibun

et. al. (2024), and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

Gathering the data, questionnaires were used to determine the factors contributing to skipping breakfast among the senior high school students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. Some questions were taken from the internet, though there were some that were slightly revised and subjected to reading by experts in the field of research who were tasked with stabilizing the content on the basis of clarity, relevance, and purity.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers collected data by first obtaining a letter of permission from the Senior High School Department Director of Mindanao State University, Sulu. A letter of permission was also sent to the respondents' class advisers to enable researchers to conduct questionnaires on the subject of skipping breakfast. When the letter was approved, the researcher personally delivered the research instrument and recovered it. The responses of the respondents were collected, verified, and compiled to obtain the original score.

Statistical Techniques

A weighted mean is used to describe the factors affecting the performance, its impact on the students, and their level of academic performance at Mindanao State University-Sulu. While the significant relationship between factors and the impact of skipping breakfast on academic performance is dealt with within correlations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Factors of Skipping Breakfast Among the Grade 11 GAS Students

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. I don't like the food choices.	2.46	.734	Yes
2. It's a habit	2.45	.747	Yes
3. My family skipped breakfast. and so do I.	2.44	.649	Yes
4. Unable to prepare	2.40	.767	Yes
5. I need to lose weight	2.40	.614	Yes
6. Away from family	2.31	.776	Maybe
7. Work pressure	2.30	.831	Maybe

8. No time to have breakfast	2.30	.810	Maybe.
9. I don't feel hungry.	2.29	.717	Maybe
10. I don't like eating early in the Morning.	2.25	.794	Maybe
Grand Mean	2.36		Yes

Legend; 1.00-1.67=No (Disagree), 1.68-2.34=Maybe (Undecided), 2.35-3.00=Yes (Agree)

Table 1 shows the results on the factors contributing to skipping breakfast among the Grade 11 GAS students. It was found out that the Grade 11 GAS students in MSU-Sulu SHS answered yes, which means they agreed on the listed factors of skipping breakfast, as it can be seen in the table that it has a grand mean of 3.26. This indicates that skipping breakfast among the Grade 11 GAS students at MSU-Sulu SHS is not a rare occurrence.

Table 2 Students' Level of Academic Performance

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Academic Performance	86.32	3.9	Very Satisfactory

Note: Did not meet the expectation= 74 and below; Fairly Satisfactory=75-8; Satisfactory = 80-84; Very Satisfactory = 85-89; and Outstanding = 90-100.

As shown in this table, the level of academic performance of grade 11 GAS students garnered a mean of 86.32% with a verbal description of satisfactory. This means that the level of academic performance of grade 11 GAS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School is very satisfactory, which signifies that they are not affected by the factors of skipping breakfast.

Table 3 Impact of Skipping Breakfast Among the Grade 11 GAS Students

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1.I always feel the lack of concentration during class sessions.	1.79	.829	Maybe
2.I have experienced feeling tired or fatigue in the morning due to skipping breakfast.	1.75	.704	Maybe
3. Lack of class participation lead into my poor performance.	1.74	.797	Maybe
4.Skipping breakfast can affect my academic	1.63	.763	No

performance or ability to learn.			
5. Skipping breakfast can affect my academic performance or ability to learn.	1.62	.671	No
6. Skipping breakfast can have an impact to my brain function and subsequent performance.	1.55	.695	No
7. Skipping breakfast can make an impacts on my performance in exams or tests.	1.55	.671	No
8. I have experienced a decline in my academic performance.	1.55	.650	No
9. I have experienced low energy level during the school I day.	1.55	.604	No
10. I often find myself feeling hungry or distracted during morning classes when I skip breakfast.	1.52	.539	No
Grand Mean	1.47		No

Legend; 1.00-1.67=No (Disagree), 1.68-2.34=Maybe (Undecided), 2.35-3.00=Yes (Agree)

Table 2 shows the perceived impact of skipping breakfast on the academic performance of Grade 11 GAS students. It was found that the grade 11 students perceived that the lists of possible impacts of skipping breakfast on student academic performance were not true to them. The grand mean obtained was 1.47 with a verbal description of no, which means disagree. Pollitt and Mathew (1998) summarized the literature on the impact of breakfast on cognition, finding that no definitive conclusion was justified. However, they found that the data strongly suggests that omitting breakfast interferes with perception and learning, which is more pronounced in nutritionally vulnerable students. But despite skipping breakfast, the students still manage to do very well in their academic performance in school.

Table 4. Relationship of Factors of skipping breakfast to the academic performance of GAS grade 11

Variables	1	2
Factors of Skipping Breakfast	-	
General Average	.273**	-

Note: " $p < .05$ ", " $p < .01$ ".

A Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to assess the linear relationship between factors of skipping breakfast and the academic performance of the students. The findings revealed that there is a correlation between the two variables, $r(103) = -.273^{**}$, $p = .005$.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the factors of skipping breakfast showed that the students of MSU-Sulu SHS Grade 11 GAS have said "yes, which means the students agreed about the factors of skipping breakfast. In terms of the level of academic performance among students at MSU-Sulu Senior High School, it was assessed as very satisfactory." This means that there is a great level of satisfaction, even though the student has perceived the factors of skipping breakfast. The impact of skipping breakfast among the students of MSU-Sulu Senior High School Grade 11 GAS has been said "NO" which means the students did not perceive the statements, but the students are still able to gain very satisfactory results in their academic performance. The relationship between factors such as skipping breakfast and students' academic performance is not related. Based on research findings, there are reasons for skipping breakfast that did not have an impact on the students' academic performance.

Recommendations

1. Increase awareness and education. It is crucial to raise awareness among students, parents, and educators about the importance of breakfast for academic performance. Conduct workshops, seminars, or informational sessions to educate them about the benefits of a nutritious breakfast and the potential consequences of skipping it.
2. Improve breakfast options: Collaborate with school cafeterias or food service providers to offer a variety of healthy and appealing breakfast options. Ensure that the available choices are nutritious, balanced, and cater to different dietary preferences and restrictions.
3. The school may create a breakfast-friendly environment. Establish a positive and inviting breakfast environment within the school premises.
4. The school may designate a dedicated breakfast area where students can comfortably enjoy their meals. Consider incorporating socialization opportunities, such as breakfast clubs or peer support groups, to encourage regular breakfast consumption.
5. Implement breakfast programs. Develop and implement breakfast programs that provide students with access to a nutritious breakfast, especially for those who may face financial constraints or time limitations at home. These programs can include initiatives such as grab-and-go breakfasts, breakfast in the classroom, or breakfast vouchers.
- 6: The concerned school may engage with parents and guardians in promoting a healthy breakfast, habits at home. Provide them with resources, such as recipe ideas or meal planning tips, to support them in preparing nutritious breakfasts for their children.

7. The teachers may continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented interventions. Collect data on breakfast consumption rates, academic performance, and student feedback to assess the impact of the initiatives and identify areas for improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers have guaranteed that participants in the study will have the freedom to check and respond to the questionnaire provided. Furthermore, the researchers ensure that the questionnaire is readable and concise.

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